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ASSESSMENT OF ALTERNATIVE CONSTRUCTION PROJECT
DELIVERY METHODS: EVIDENCE FROM WEST GUJI ZONE,
ETHIOPIA

BY

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Assessment of Alternative Construction Project Delivery Methods: Evidence
from West Guji Zone, Ethiopia

By

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List of Acronomy

<i>APDM</i>	<i>Alternative project delivery methods</i>
<i>CMAR</i>	<i>Construction Management-at-Risk</i>
CSFs	Critical success factors
CM	Construction Management
<i>DB</i>	<i>Design-Build, delivery methods</i>
<i>DBB</i>	<i>Design-Build-Bid</i>
<i>ETB</i>	<i>Ethiopian birr</i>
FA	Force account method
<i>GDP</i>	<i>gross domestic product</i>
<i>JOC</i>	<i>Job Order Contracting</i>
<i>PPP</i>	<i>Public Private Partnership</i>
<i>PSS</i>	<i>Statistical Package for Social Scientists</i>
PCS	public construction sector
<i>RII</i>	<i>Relative Importance Index</i>
KPIs	key performance indicator
SNNPR	Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples' Region

Abstract

This study evaluates alternative construction project delivery methods for public construction projects in the West Guji Zone of Ethiopia. Traditional Design-Bid-Build (DBB) approaches have shown significant inefficiencies, including delays, cost overruns, and quality challenges. To address this issue, the research assesses alternative delivery methods such as Design-Build (DB), Construction Management at Risk (CMAR), Job Order Contracting (JOC), and Force Account. A mixed-method approach was employed, combining questionnaire data from 56 construction professionals with qualitative interviews. Quantitative analysis, including Relative Importance Index (RII) and reliability testing, was used to evaluate performance based on cost, time, and quality criteria. The findings indicate that alternative delivery methods, particularly Design-Build and CMAR, demonstrate improved efficiency and better project performance compared to traditional methods. The study proposes a practical evaluation framework to support decision-making in selecting appropriate delivery systems for public construction projects. The results contribute to improving project delivery practices in developing countries and provide insights for policymakers and practitioners in Ethiopia. The findings provide practical implications for improving construction project delivery systems in developing countries.

Keywords:

Construction Project Delivery Methods; Design-Build (DB); Construction Management at Risk (CMAR); Public Construction Projects; Project Performance; Ethiopia; West Guji Zone.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Study Background

Public construction projects are often complex and involve various stakeholders, regulations, and challenges. Traditional project delivery methods may not always be the most efficient or cost-effective for public projects the problem revolves around the need to identify and assess alternative project delivery methods that can improve the efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and timely completion of public construction projects. There is a gap in understanding the various alternative methods available and their potential benefits and drawbacks in the context of public projects[1].

The genesis of this problem lies in the recognition that traditional project delivery methods may not adequately address the evolving needs and challenges of public infrastructure projects. By understanding the limitations of existing approaches and exploring alternative delivery methods, stakeholders can optimize project outcomes in terms of cost, schedule, quality, risk management, and innovation. Conducting a comprehensive study on assessing these alternative project delivery methods provides valuable insights and guidance for decision-makers tasked with selecting the most suitable approach for public construction projects[2].

In many parts of the world, traditional project delivery methods, such as design-bid-build, are being supplemented or replaced by alternative approaches like design-build, construction management at risk (CMAR), and public-private partnerships (PPP). These alternative methods offer various benefits, including faster project delivery, enhanced collaboration among project stakeholders, better risk management, and improved project outcomes[3]. However, the suitability and effectiveness of these alternative delivery methods can vary depending on local contexts, including economic conditions, legal frameworks, institutional capacities, and cultural factors. In the case of the West Guji Zone of Oromia, Ethiopia,

several factors need to be considered when assessing alternative project delivery methods for public construction projects.[4]

Understanding the global best practices and tailoring them to the local context of the West Guji Zone in Oromia/Ethiopia is essential for conducting a comprehensive study on assessing alternative project delivery methods for public construction projects in the region. This approach can help address the infrastructure development needs and contribute to sustainable development in the area.[5]

The public construction sector in the West Guji/Oromia region is pivotal in the development of crucial infrastructure essential for societal progress. This emphasis on infrastructure development is vital in providing employment opportunities for a significant portion of the population, including engineers, architects, construction workers, and supporting staff. Local contractors and construction companies are actively engaged in executing government projects, playing a critical role in infrastructure development and local economic growth. Additionally, collaborations with national and international partners, development agencies, and organizations are part of the sector's approach to funding and implementing construction projects that benefit the region[6][7].

Operating within a regulatory framework established by government entities, the public construction sector in Ethiopia adheres to defined standards, guidelines, and procedures to ensure the quality and safety of construction projects. Despite its growth and importance, the sector faces challenges such as funding constraints, project implementation delays, inadequacy of skilled labor, and issues related to project management and coordination.[8]

This sector serves as the backbone of societal progress and economic development, both locally and nationally within specific regions like Ethiopia and its prominent Oromiya region. Public construction projects are instrumental in promoting connectivity, accessibility, and enhancing the quality of life for communities by developing critical infrastructure such as roads, bridges, schools, hospitals, and utilities. Consequently, the exploration of alternative project delivery methods, such as Design-Build (DB), Construction Management

at Risk (CMAR), Job Order Contracting (JOC) and Force account delivery methods, aims to address challenges faced by traditional linear approaches and improve efficiency and effectiveness in infrastructure development. These alternative methods have the potential to streamline project delivery processes, promote collaboration among stakeholders, and enhance project outcomes on a global scale.[9][2]

Although significant strides have been made in the public construction sector, several challenges persist, including limited funding, capacity constraints, regulatory complexities, and institutional inefficiencies. Overcoming these challenges and enhancing project outcomes require tailored approaches to project planning, procurement, and execution, particularly in diverse regions like Oromiya. This research should focus on addressing these challenges and optimizing project delivery strategies to ensure sustainable infrastructure development and economic growth in the region.

By targeting these diverse groups of stakeholders, the study can gather a comprehensive range of perspectives on alternative project delivery methods for public construction projects in the West Guji Zone. This inclusive approach helps ensure that the findings and recommendations of the study are relevant, practical, and reflective of the needs and priorities of the local community and broader stakeholders involved in infrastructure development.

The core problem/issue that the research seeks to investigate and analyze can be outlined as follows: Challenges in Traditional Project Delivery: The existing traditional project delivery methods for public construction projects in the West Guji Zone may face inefficiencies, delays, cost overruns, and quality issues. This can impact the timely completion of projects and hinder their overall success. Need for Improved Project Delivery Practices there is a growing recognition of the need to explore and adopt alternative project delivery methods that can enhance the performance and outcomes of public construction projects in the region. This includes considering innovative approaches to project planning, implementation, and management. Variety of Delivery Methods[10] The study aims to examine a range of alternative project delivery methods such as Design-Bid-Build, Design-Build, and

Construction Management at Risk (CMAR), Job order Contracting (JOR) and Force account method (FA) other emerging models. Understanding the strengths and weaknesses of each method is crucial for selecting the most suitable approach for different project scenarios. Local Context and Challenges the researches that take into account the specific characteristics, requirements, and challenges of the West Guji Zone in Oromia, Ethiopia.

The study focuses on evaluating alternative project delivery methods for public construction projects in the West Guji Zone of Oromia, Ethiopia, addressing critical issues such as inefficiencies in traditional methods, quality and sustainability concerns, as well as growth and development needs. It employs a structured research methodology involving a literature review, data collection, analysis, and evaluation to systematically explore challenges and opportunities in project delivery practices. Through this approach, the study aims to provide valuable insights and actionable recommendations for enhancing the efficiency, effectiveness, and sustainability of public construction projects in the region. Key terms essential for understanding the study include project delivery methods, stakeholders, quality, sustainability, cost-effectiveness, risk management, regulatory requirements, and legal compliance. Understanding these terms is crucial for knowing the complexities of alternative project delivery methods in the West Guji Zone of Oromiya.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Public construction projects in the West Guji Zone of Oromiya, Ethiopia, are predominantly managed using traditional project delivery methods such as Design-Bid-Build (DBB). These conventional methods have exhibited significant inefficiencies, including delays, cost overruns, and quality issues, which obstruct the successful and timely completion of projects. This problem is worsened by several factors unique to the region, such as insufficient communication and coordination among stakeholders, delays in progress payments, and financial constraints [6] [11]. The existing legal frameworks in Ethiopia further compound these challenges by favoring traditional DBB methods, despite the potential benefits of alternative methods like Design-Build (DB) and Construction Management at Risk (CMAR). These alternative methods are underutilized due to regulatory and institutional obstacles, limiting innovation and efficiency in project delivery.

Particular the rapid development and expanding infrastructure needs of the West Guji Zone, there is a pressing need to explore and adopt alternative project delivery methods that can enhance project performance in terms of cost, time, and quality. This study aims to evaluate these alternative methods, considering the specific characteristics and challenges of the region, and propose practical solutions that improve the efficiency and effectiveness of public construction projects.

By addressing these issues, the research seeks to contribute to better infrastructure development, economic growth, and sustainable development in the West Guji Zone, ultimately benefiting the local community and broader stakeholders involved in public construction projects.

1.3. General Objective.

The main objective of the study is to assess alternative project delivery methods for public construction projects in the West Guji Zone of Oromia, Ethiopia.

1.3.1. Specific Objective

1. To assess the current project delivery practices in west Guji zone public construction works.
2. To determine the effectiveness of alternative project delivery systems in terms of cost, time, and quality in the west Guji zone
3. To develop idea of framework for measuring the performance of different project delivery approaches in the Waste Guji Zone.

1.4. Research Questions

This research aims to identify the causes behind project incompleteness/project failure and related factors. The Processes in Ethiopian public building sector organizations performance evaluation are necessary to get better result for present and for future. Thus, in order to block the research problem, the following research questions are raised:

1. What are the Current Project Delivery Practices in west Guji zone public construction works?
2. What are the factors that influence the effectiveness of alternative project delivery systems in terms of cost time and quality in the study area?
3. What is a framework for measuring the performance of different project delivery approaches?

1.5. Justification/Rationale/motivation

The rationale for undertaking the study on assessing alternative project delivery methods for public construction projects in the West Guji Zone of Oromia, Ethiopia, is multi-faceted and compelling.

Firstly, traditional project delivery methods have exhibited inefficiencies that hinder progress and result in suboptimal outcomes. These inefficiencies may include delays, cost overruns, and quality issues, ultimately impacting the overall success of public construction projects.

Secondly, there are significant concerns regarding the quality and sustainability of construction projects in the region. Addressing these concerns is crucial for ensuring the long-term viability and environmental responsibility of infrastructure development initiatives. Moreover, as the West Guji Zone experiences growth and development, there is a pressing need to optimize resources and enhance project delivery practices to support the region's evolving infrastructure requirements.

Furthermore, engaging stakeholders effectively and incorporating regional and national best practices are vital for fostering collaboration, ensuring alignment with community needs, and promoting successful project outcomes.

Additionally, building capacity and transferring knowledge regarding alternative project delivery methods can empower local stakeholders to adopt innovative approaches, leading to improved project performance and outcomes.

In summary, the study's justification stems from the imperative to address inefficiencies in traditional methods, tackle quality and sustainability concerns, support growth and

development needs, optimize resources, enhance stakeholder engagement, and promote capacity building and knowledge transfer in public construction projects within the West Guji Zone of Oromia, Ethiopia.

1.6. Scope of Study

This research is geographically limited to Ethiopia, specifically in the west Guji zone. Even though the construction industry includes numerous firms and stakeholders, the scope of this study was limited to Public Construction Project only and the respondents were limited to construction professionals who are directly involved in Public construction projects in west Guji zone.

1.7. Structure of the Study

Research writing is the final step of the study and it contains five main chapters. These are the introduction, literature review, research methodology, data analysis and discussions, Conclusion and Recommendation.

Chapter One: Introduction: *This chapter comprised the background of the study, problem statement, aim and objectives, significance and challenges of the study, and structure of the research Conclusion and recommendations.*

Chapter Two: Literature Review: *The literature review started with a literature exploration of electronic and hard copy media in answering the research objectives. Next, the chapter discusses the performance of public construction projects*

Chapter Three: Research Methodology: *This chapter discussed the tools and methods used for data collection. The use of techniques and tools for collecting and analyzing data led to a critical review of the analysis and established an identified gap in the research question including the aim and object.*

Chapter Four: Data Analysis and Discussions: *This chapter organized the analysis of data gathered with the research instruments*

***Chapter Five: Conclusion and Remedial Measure:** This is the final chapter of the research in which conclusions and recommendations were drawn based upon the analysis data, linking them to the problem statement and objectives of the study.*

CHAPTER TWO-LITERATURE REVIEW

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Introduction

Public construction projects play a pivotal role in economic development, infrastructure enhancement, and societal progress globally. The efficient and effective delivery of these projects is essential to ensure timely completion, cost control, and quality outcomes. Traditional project delivery methods, such as design-bid-build, have long been the standard approach. However, evolving complexities in construction projects and the need for innovation have led to the emergence and adoption of alternative project delivery methods (PDMs) worldwide [13].

Internationally, countries have embraced alternative PDMs to varying extents, driven by factors such as project complexity, funding mechanisms, and regulatory frameworks. In regions like North America and Europe, DB and CMAR have gained prominence due to their potential for streamlining project delivery and fostering innovation[17]. PPPs have emerged as a strategic tool for leveraging private sector expertise and investment in infrastructure development across diverse sectors and geographies[8]. Moreover, collaborative approaches like IPD have garnered attention for their ability to enhance communication, integration, and risk management throughout the project lifecycle. In Ethiopia, the construction sector plays a vital role in the country's economic growth and social development agenda. However, challenges such as limited funding, capacity constraints, and institutional barriers have underscored the need for alternative PDMs to address inefficiencies and improve project delivery outcomes. As Ethiopia strives to accelerate infrastructure development and achieve sustainable development goals, exploring and adapting international best practices in project delivery methods becomes imperative. Factors such as legal frameworks, institutional capabilities, and cultural dynamics shape the feasibility and effectiveness of alternative PDMs in the Ethiopian context.[10]

This literature review aims to comprehensively assess alternative project delivery methods for public construction projects, both internationally and in Ethiopia/Oromiya west guji zone.

By synthesizing existing research, case studies, and best practices, it seeks to: Evaluate the advantages, challenges, and applicability of alternative PDMs in different project environments. Identify successful implementation strategies, lessons learned, and critical success factors from international experiences.

Analyze the contextual factors influencing the adoption and effectiveness of alternative PDMs in Ethiopia. Provide insights and recommendations for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers to enhance project delivery practices and outcomes in Ethiopia's construction sector.

2.2. Structure of the Literature Review

The literature review will be organized into several sections, including: Overview of traditional and alternative project delivery methods.

Comparative analysis of alternative PDMs, including DB, CMAR, DBB, and Job Order Contracting and Force Account delivery Methods.

International perspectives on the adoption and implementation of alternative PDMs.

Specific considerations and challenges related to alternative project delivery in Ethiopia.

Identification of barriers and facilitators for the adoption of alternative PDMs.

Promoting the effective use of alternative PDMs in Ethiopia's/or Omiya west guji zone public construction project.

2.3 Project Delivery Methods

Selecting the appropriate project delivery method is one of the most important managerial decisions as it has a direct impact on the success of the project since it affects key performance indicators such as cost, quality, schedule, and safety. Project delivery methods have evolved over the years, with many variations and alternatives introduced in the construction industry to meet various consumer demands. The AGC (2004) defines project delivery method as the comprehensive process of assigning the contractual responsibilities for designing and constructing a project[18]. It identifies the primary parties taking

contractual responsibility for the performance of the work. The Texas DOT (2001) defines project delivery method as a procurement approach that defines the relationships, roles, and responsibilities of project team members and sequences of activities required to complete a project.

Project delivery methods have evolved to address the various ways in which contracting parties which to allocate their risk, from traditional stipulated price/general contracts to the development of alternative financing and procurement methods. Each project delivery method has its advantages and disadvantages, and it is the role of the construction solicitor to ensure that clients are protected to the greatest extent possible against the risks they choose to accept. Gaining and maintaining control of the design process is a critical element for controlling the cost, schedule, and scope of a project. Failure to control and manage this process can lead to delays and increased construction costs.

The size and complexity of projects have increased, making the ability to manage risks throughout the construction process crucial in preventing unwanted consequences. Different project risks need to be allocated to the project's actors based on their qualifications for dealing with specific risks. Selecting an appropriate project delivery option is a key issue for project actors. Projects can be designed and constructed in various combinations to deliver a complete and usable facility, with delivery mechanisms such as construction management at risk, construction management agency, program management, multiple-prime contracting, DB, and DBB. in the context of this research, a project delivery system is defined as the roles, interactions, and obligations of contracted parties and the sequence of activities necessary for providing a facility project from design concept initiation to final construction completion.[16]

This research study evaluates the main project delivery systems, including DB, DBB, Construction Management at fee and Risk, Job Order Contracting, and Force account Delivery. Each system is based on different fundamental commitments to the project owner. This research study builds on previous studies conducted on public construction projects and uses questionnaire interviews as a survey method. It is based on previously completed DBB projects and ongoing DB projects. Literature reviews on previous studies are analyzed,

compared, and interpreted to address the current research problem. The motivation behind this research study is to find solutions to the delivery method problems faced by West Guji Zone public projects, create awareness of the alternatives available, and help the West Guji Zone public authority adopt a more productive delivery method that meets schedules and keeps costs manageable. Several DB options are considered, including design professional as the DB entity, general contractor as the DB entity, joint ventures, and DB companies with in-house design and construction capabilities.

2.4. Historical Perspective of Delivery Methods

The evolution of Design-Build (DB), Design-Bid-Build (DBB), Construction Management at Fee and Risk, Job Order Contracting, and Force Account Delivery methods has been influenced by the changing needs of the construction industry. Each of these delivery methods has a unique historical perspective:

Design-Build (DB): The DB delivery method traces back to ancient times when master builders were responsible for both designing and constructing buildings. In the modern era, DB gained popularity in the United States in the 1960s as a collaborative and streamlined alternative to the traditional Design-Bid-Build method. It has become widely used for fostering teamwork, reducing project duration, and mitigating disputes between design and construction teams.

Design-Bid-Build (DBB): DBB has been the traditional approach to construction for centuries. In this method, an architect is first commissioned to design the project, and then the completed design is put out to bid for contractors to compete on price. DBB was dominant for many years due to its perceived transparency and accountability, but the DB approach gained traction as projects became more complex and stakeholders sought greater efficiency.

. Construction Management at Fee and Risk: Construction Management (CM) emerged in the United States in the 1970s in response to the increased complexity of construction projects. In CM, the construction manager is contracted by the owner to oversee the entire construction process. CM at Fee involves the construction manager being paid a fixed fee for

their services, while CM at Risk involves the construction manager assuming financial risk for the project's cost and schedule performance.

Job Order Contracting (JOC): Job Order Contracting is a newer delivery method that originated in the public sector in the 1980s. JOC involves establishing a long-term relationship between an owner and contractor through pre-priced contracts for recurring construction, maintenance, and repair projects. It is known for its flexibility, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness, making it popular for owners with a high volume of small to medium-sized projects.

Force Account Delivery: Force Account Delivery is the most direct and hands-on method of project delivery, where the owner directly hires and supervises the construction workforce and procures materials and equipment for the project. It is typically used for emergency repairs, small-scale projects, or projects with uncertain requirements where traditional contracting methods may not be suitable.

In conclusion, the historical evolution of these construction delivery methods reflects the industry's ongoing efforts to improve collaboration, efficiency, and risk management in construction projects. Each method offers unique advantages and challenges, with their adoption varying based on the project's scope, complexity, and stakeholder preferences[19].

2.5. DBB project delivery system

According to Department of the Air Force, 2000 DBB is defined as: “the project delivery approach where the Owner commissions an architect or engineer to prepare drawings and specifications under a design services contract, and separately contracts for at-risk construction, by engaging a contractor through competitive bidding or negotiation.” (DBIA, 2007a) Federal laws and regulations mandated the use of the DBB method for the public sector [8]. The traditional method is a simple process to manage that is well understood by owners, designers, and builders (Department of the Air Force, 2000). This method appealed to owners due to its established track record, the complete control over project design, and the award given to the lowest bidder from competitive bidding [3]

The Design-Bid-Build (DBB) project delivery system, also known as the traditional or conventional project delivery method, is a linear and sequential approach to construction projects. In the DBB method, the project is divided into three main phases: design, bid, and build. Here is an overview of how the DBB project delivery system works:[20]

2.5.1 Design Phase:

The project owner selects an architect or design team to develop the project's design and specifications based on the owner's requirements and budget.

The architect completes the design documents, including drawings, specifications, and other contract documents, detailing the scope of work and project requirements. During the design phase, the owner and architect work closely together to finalize the design and obtain necessary approvals from regulatory authorities.

2.5.2. Bid Phase:

Once the design documents are complete, the owner puts the project out to bid by soliciting competitive bids from general contractors or construction firms. Contractors review the design documents and submit sealed bids that outline the cost of construction, project schedule, and any proposed alternatives or value engineering options. The owner evaluates the bids based on criteria such as price, experience, qualifications, and schedule and selects the contractor with the most competitive bid to proceed with the project.

2.5.3. Build Phase:

After awarding the contract to the selected contractor, the construction phase begins, and the contractor mobilizes the necessary resources, labor, and materials to start construction[21]. The contractor is responsible for coordinating the construction activities, managing subcontractors, ensuring quality control, and adhering to the project schedule and budget. Throughout the construction phase, the architect or a project manager may provide oversight and address any design-related issues or changes that arise during construction.

The Design-Bid-Build project delivery system is characterized by a clear separation of design and construction responsibilities. While this method offers transparency and

accountability during the bidding process, it can sometimes lead to adversarial relationships between the design and construction teams and potential delays or cost overruns due to design discrepancies or changes.[22]

Overall, the DBB project delivery system has been widely used in the construction industry for many years and remains a common choice for public sector projects and certain private sector projects where the owner seeks competitive pricing and clear delineation of roles between the design and construction teams.

It is known that no one project delivery method is flawless. The advantages and disadvantages of the DBB method are shown in table 2.2. This may not include all the advantages and disadvantages known, but it does highlight the main points for a clearer understanding of this delivery method's strengths and weaknesses.

Traditional DBB procurement was the primary method used before innovative contracting was introduced in the last twenty years, primarily because of statutory public purchasing laws. In the traditional system, project award is based solely on cost, with no consideration of qualifications, schedule, or past performance. In a traditional delivery system, the design is 100% complete before the owner is able to solicit bids. The process requires the longest overall project time to completion. Also, with the design 100% complete, there is little room for the contractor to use innovative techniques that can save money and time on the project.[22]

Figure 2.1 design – bid – build (project organizational char

2.5.4. Major Stakeholders in DBB

In a typical public construction project, the contractual arrangement with an employer contractor agreement involves some of the primary stakeholders such as employer, contractor, engineer, financial institutions, and subcontractors etc. The following table (Table 2.1) shows some of the major roles of the above three primary stakeholders for a typical public construction project under a design bid build contract delivery system.

Table 2.1 Major Stakeholders in Deign Bid Built

NO	Major Stakeholder	Major Responsibilities
1	Employer	Provides financial support to develop the project Determines the scope of the work Creates the necessity to build the facility Most important player of the process
2	Engineer	Develops drawings and specifications and prepares other contract documents Administers the contract and supervises the Works Responsible for the project design Idealizes the final result of the project
3	Contractor	Brings the project into reality Manages different resources to build the facility Creates the facility based on the design

Source: - PDS on Major US Construction Project David M, 2004

Table 2.2. Advantages' and disadvantages of DBB project delivery system

NO	Advantage	Disadvantage
1	Contractors bid competitively, based on complete design documents to maximize the built product for the price	DBB construction phases are sequential and may require more time
2	The owner selects the contractor on the basis of qualifications or ability. The designer's role is that of owner's legated Representative.	Owner is at risk for final construction cost. Actual construction costs are not known until design and bidding are complete.
3	The designer is active in construction administration so design intentions are followed.	The designer is active in construction administration so design intentions are followed
4	Legal Protection: Since the design is completed before contractors are engaged, there is a clear delineation of responsibilities and liabilities, providing legal protection to the owner.	Limited Flexibility: DBB may offer limited flexibility for making design changes or adjustments during the construction phase, as the design is typically finalized before construction begins

2.6. (DB) project delivery system

In the Design-Build project delivery system, the design and construction phases are combined into a single contract between the project owner and a single entity, known as the design-build team. Here is an overview of how the Design-Build project delivery system works:

2.6.1. Selection of Design-Builder:

The project owner selects a design-build team, typically consisting of a contractor and an architect or design firm, based on qualifications, experience, and proposed approach. The

design-build team is responsible for both designing and constructing the project, providing a single point of contact for the owner throughout the project.

2.6.2. Design-Build Phase:

The design-build team collaborates closely with the owner to develop the project requirements, budget, and design concepts. The design-build team is responsible for preparing the design documents, obtaining necessary permits, and ensuring that the design meets the owner's needs and objectives. The design-build team may use a fast-track approach to streamline the design and construction process, allowing for early construction activities while design details are still being finalized.

2.6.3. Construction Phase:

Once the design is finalized and approved by the owner, the construction phase begins immediately, as the design-build team transitions seamlessly from design to construction. The design-build team is responsible for managing the construction process, coordinating subcontractors, ensuring quality control, and meeting project schedule and budget requirements. The owner has a single point of responsibility and contact throughout the project, simplifying communication and decision-making processes.

The Design-Build project delivery system offers several advantages, including faster project delivery, cost efficiency, streamlined communication, and potential for innovation and collaboration between the design and construction teams. By integrating design and construction under one contract, the design-build approach can help reduce project risks, minimize conflicts, and promote teamwork among project stakeholders.

Overall, the Design-Build project delivery system is a popular alternative to the traditional Design-Bid-Build method, preferred by many owners seeking a more streamlined and efficient construction process with a single entity accountable for both design and construction.

Figure.2.2 design-build (project organization)

Table 2.3 an advantages and Disadvantages of DB Project Delivery System

NO	Advantage	Disadvantage
.1	Single point of responsibility: The owner deals with only one entity, simplifying communication and accountability	Limited owner control: Owners may have less involvement in the design process compared to traditional methods.
2	Faster project delivery: Concurrent design and construction phases can expedite project completion	Potential for conflicts of interest: The design-builder may prioritize cost savings over quality or design aesthetics.

2.7. Construction Management both @ Fee and Risk project delivery system.

The Construction Management at Risk (CMAR) project delivery system combines elements of both the Construction Management (CM) approach and the Design-Build method,

providing owners with a collaborative and risk-sharing method for project delivery. In the CMAR model, the construction manager is hired by the owner early in the project development stage to provide input during the design process, estimate project costs, and manage the construction phase. Here is an overview of the Construction Management at Risk (CMAR) project delivery system, including both fee-based and risk-based aspects:[8]

2.7.1. Construction Management (CM) Fee-Based Approach:

In the CM fee-based approach, the construction manager is typically hired on a fee basis and serves as the owner's representative throughout the project. The construction manager provides pre-construction services, such as cost estimating, scheduling, value engineering, and constructability reviews, to assist the owner and design team in developing a well-coordinated project. The construction manager acts as a partner to the owner, offering expertise in construction methods, materials, and costs, and helping to ensure that the project meets the owner's objectives.

2.7.2. Construction Management at Risk (CMAR) Risk-Based Approach:

In the CMAR risk-based approach, the construction manager is not only involved in the pre-construction phase but also assumes additional project risks during the construction phase. The construction manager at risk guarantees the project's cost and schedule, taking on financial responsibility for any cost overruns or delays that occur during construction.

By assuming these risks, the construction manager at risk has a vested interest in managing the project efficiently, controlling costs, and delivering the project on time and within budget.

Key Features of CMAR Project Delivery System: Early Involvement: The construction manager is engaged early in the project to provide input during the design phase, fostering collaboration and value engineering opportunities. Cost and Schedule Guarantees: The construction manager at risk guarantees the project's cost and schedule, providing the owner with more certainty and accountability.

Risk Sharing: The CMAR model allows for the sharing of project risks between the owner and the construction manager, promoting a collaborative and transparent approach.

Overall, the Construction Management at Risk (CMAR) project delivery system combines the expertise of the construction manager with a shared risk model, offering owners a comprehensive and collaborative approach to project delivery that emphasizes cost certainty, schedule accountability, and quality construction.[12]

Figure 2.3. Construction management (cm) at risk (project organizational chart)

Table 2.4 Advantages and Disadvantages of CMA) Project Delivery System

No	Advantages	Disadvantages
1	Early cost certainty: The construction manager provides cost estimates early in the project, helping owners manage budgets more effectively.	Potential for conflicts of interest: Construction managers may prioritize cost-saving measures that conflict with the owner's preferences
2	Collaboration and expertise: Owners can benefit from the construction manager's expertise in project planning, scheduling, and risk management	Complex contracts: CMAR contracts can be intricate, requiring careful negotiation and management to ensure alignment of interests.
3	Flexibility: CMAR allows for adjustments during the design and construction phases, accommodating changes or unforeseen challenges more easily.	Higher upfront costs: Owners may incur higher initial costs due to the involvement of a construction manager throughout the project lifecycle

2.8. Job Order Contracting project delivery system.

Job Order Contracting (JOC) is a construction project delivery method that is commonly used for renovation, repair, and construction projects that require multiple, repetitive tasks. JOC is a procurement method that allows owners to efficiently complete a series of projects through a single, competitively-awarded contract.

2.8.1. Framework Agreement:

In the JOC system, the owner enters into a framework agreement with a contractor, also known as the Job Order Contractor. This agreement outlines the terms and conditions under which individual projects will be completed.

2.8.2. Unit Price Book: A Unit Price Book (UPB) is a critical component of JOC. The UPB contains pre-established unit prices for various construction tasks and materials, allowing for quick and efficient pricing of change orders and additional work.

2.8.3. Indefinite Delivery

Indefinite Quantity (IDIQ): JOC contracts typically operate on an Indefinite Delivery, Indefinite Quantity (IDIQ) basis. This means that the owner can issue work orders within the contract's scope without specifying a precise quantity, providing flexibility for ongoing and future projects.

2.8.4. Competitive Task Order Pricing:

When a project arises, the owner issues a task order to the Job Order Contractor. The contractor then submits a price proposal based on the unit prices in the UPB, with any applicable adjustments for scope, site conditions, or other factors.

2.8.5. Streamlined Procurement Process:

The JOC process streamlines the procurement of construction services for smaller, repetitive projects by eliminating the need to go through a lengthy bidding process for each individual project.

2.8.6. Rapid Project Delivery:

JOC facilitates the rapid delivery of projects by leveraging pre-established unit prices, procedures, and a collaborative relationship between the owner and the Job Order Contractor.

2.8.7. Collaboration and Transparency:

JOC encourages collaboration and transparency between the owner, contractor, and subcontractors throughout the project lifecycle, fostering a partnership-based approach to project delivery.

Benefits of Job Order Contracting (JOC) include: Time and Cost Savings: JOC can reduce procurement time, streamline project delivery, and provide cost certainty through pre-established unit prices. Flexibility: JOC allows for quick response to changing project needs and the completion of multiple projects under a single contract. Efficiency and Quality: The JOC system promotes efficient project delivery and quality construction through standardized processes and pricing[23].

Overall, Job Order Contracting (JOC) is a project delivery system that offers an efficient, collaborative, and cost-effective approach for completing multiple construction projects with repetitive scopes of work.

Figure 2.4 job order contracting (project organizational chart)

Table 2.5 an advantages and Disadvantages of Job Order Contracting Project Delivery

NO	Advantages	Disadvantages
1	Streamlined procurement: JOC streamlines the procurement process for repetitive, smaller-scale projects, reducing administrative burden and time	Limited scope: JOC is best suited for smaller projects with similar characteristics limiting its applicability for larger or more complex endeavors.
2	Flexibility and responsiveness: JOC allows for quick project initiation and adjustments, ideal for urgent or unforeseen maintenance needs.	Potential for scope creep: Without proper management, projects under JOC contracts may expand beyond their initial scope, leading to cost overruns.
3	Cost control: Unit price contracts and predefined task orders help control costs and minimize surprises	Dependency on contractor availability: Availability of contractors may impact project scheduling and timelines.

2.9. Force account Delivery methods

Force account is a project delivery method used in construction when unforeseen circumstances or emergencies require immediate action and there is no time for the traditional bidding and contracting process. In a force account delivery method, work is typically completed by the owner's forces or by a selected contractor on a time and material basis. Force account can be an effective approach when time is of the essence and strict procurement procedures may delay critical work.[21]

There are two main force account delivery methods:

2.9.1. Owner's Force Account:

In this method, the owner uses their own employees, equipment, and resources to perform the necessary work. The owner directly manages and oversees the project, including labor, materials, and equipment procurement. This approach is commonly used for small-scale projects or urgent repairs where immediate action is required.

2.9.2. Contractor Force Account:

In this method, the owner selects a contractor to perform the work on a time and material basis. The contractor is responsible for providing labor, equipment, and materials to complete the project within a specific timeframe. The contractor's costs, including labor rates, equipment rental fees, and material costs, are reimbursed by the owner based on actual expenses.

Features of force account delivery methods include: Force account allows for flexibility in project execution, as work can begin immediately without the need for a formal bidding process. Force account delivery methods enable quick mobilization and completion of work in emergency situations or when time is limited. Both owner's force account and contractor force account provide transparency in project costs, as expenses are incurred on a time and material basis and are documented for reimbursement.

Risk Management: Force account can help mitigate risks associated with unforeseen circumstances by providing a direct and controlled approach to project delivery.

While force account delivery methods offer expedited solutions for urgent construction needs, it is important to ensure proper documentation, oversight, and communication to effectively manage the project and maintain accountability. Additionally, owners should consider other project delivery methods for planned or larger-scale construction projects where competitive bidding and formal contracts are more appropriate.

Table 2.7 Advantage and Disadvantage of Force Account Delivery

No	Advantages	Disadvantages
1	Owner control: FAPD allows owners direct control over project execution, enabling them to make real-time decisions and adjustments	Administrative burden: Owners are responsible for managing various aspects of the project, including procurement, scheduling, and quality control, which can be resource-intensive.
2	Cost transparency: Owners have visibility into project costs, including labor, materials, and equipment, promoting accountability and cost control	Skill and expertise requirements: Owners must possess or hire the necessary skills and expertise to effectively manage and oversee the project, which can be challenging.
3	Flexibility: FAPD can adapt to changing project requirements or conditions more easily compared to other delivery methods.	Risk exposure: Owners assume greater risk, including potential delays, quality issues, and cost overruns, without the support of a contracted entity.

2.10. Research Gaps in Literature

This section identifies and addresses gaps found in the current body of literature regarding alternative delivery methods in public construction projects, particularly focusing on their effectiveness in terms of cost, time, and quality. The review of literature has revealed several critical gaps that this study aims to fill:

Lack of Context-Specific Studies Existing research primarily focuses on developed countries with well-established construction industries and regulatory frameworks. There is a significant gap in studies that address the unique challenges and conditions of public construction projects in developing countries, specifically Ethiopia.

Limited Comparative Analyses Most literature evaluates individual project delivery methods in isolation without comprehensive comparative analyses that could provide insights into the relative advantages and disadvantages of various methods under different conditions.

Insufficient Stakeholder Perspective There is a lack of research that incorporates the perspectives of all key stakeholders (clients, consultants, and contractors) involved in public construction projects. Understanding their views on the effectiveness of different delivery methods can provide a more holistic view of the challenges and potential solutions.

Gap in Long-Term Performance Data Few studies have longitudinal data assessing the long-term performance and sustainability of projects delivered through alternative methods. This gap makes it difficult to determine the enduring benefits and potential pitfalls of these methods over time.

Need for Framework Development There is an identified need for the development of robust frameworks that can effectively measure and compare the performance of different project delivery methods. Current literature lacks standardized metrics and evaluation criteria that can be universally applied to assess cost, time, quality, and stakeholder satisfaction.

Impact of Local Context The influence of local context, including cultural, legal, and economic factors, on the effectiveness of alternative project delivery methods is under-researched. Most studies do not account for how these contextual factors might alter the outcomes of project delivery methods. This study aims to address these gaps by focusing on the West Guji Zone in the Oromia region of Ethiopia, providing a context-specific analysis that includes comparative evaluation, stakeholder perspectives, long-term performance data, and a developed framework for measuring project delivery effectiveness. By doing so, it seeks to contribute valuable insights and practical recommendations for improving public construction project outcomes in similar contexts.

CHAPTER-THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter introduces and describes the approaches and techniques that the researcher utilized to gather information and investigate the research problem. The chapter essentially highlighted the research scheme, research plan, and evolution processes that were adopted after the collection of the questionnaires. It included the research purpose, study population, sample size and selection, data analyzing methods and procedure, data collection methods, data quality control (validity and reliability), Ethical consideration, and Plan for dissemination.

3.2. Study Area

The research was conduct in West Guji zone which is one of the southern Oromia zones of the Ethiopia and Located in and bordered on the south by Borena, on the west by the Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples Region, on the north by the Gedeo Zone of Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples Region and Sidama Region and on the east by the Guji Zone. Its administrative center is Bule Hora Town which is located around 467km from Addis Ababa.

Figure

3.1 map showing the location of the West Guji Zone in Ethiopia

3.3. Research Design

The research process began with the identification of the problem, which was accomplished ended a review of the literature and casual conversations with experts in the construction industry. Next, the research design was developed. Next, using the developed study design as a guide, data and information sources were identified. The selection of research instruments was based on data sources, and an evaluation of relevant documentary sources was conducted.

This study falls under the descriptive research type and is classified under both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies. Through questionnaires and interviews, the researcher has gathered and examined the thoughts and perspectives of respondents and their corresponding stakeholders. The study's general methodologies are displayed in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Research Design Frameworks

The paper discusses the many delivery techniques that are currently used in public construction, their effects on cost, schedule, and quality, as well as the suitable framework

measurement that this study has desired. The study's analysis, findings, conclusions, values, and validity are all strongly impacted by the data collection techniques. A qualitative method, from a theoretical standpoint, aims to acquire understanding and comprehend people's worldviews. Both qualitative and quantitative methods are used in this study.

3.4. Data Collection Sources

In order to completely accomplish the study's stated goals, primary and secondary data sources were used.

3.4.1 Primary source

The primary data was collected directly from the respondents directly. In this method, the data was gathered by questionnaire and interview by the researcher directly from the selected and informed respondents under study consideration.

3.4.2 Secondary source

To introduce the theoretical literature of the subject, the researcher used the following data sources: data from the west guji zone (Zonal and district level construction office), Books, journal papers, and references; Journals, papers, and theses; Internet and its electronic version.

3.5. Method of Data Collection/ Procedure

Together, the qualitative and quantitative data required for this study were collected through; questionnaires and interviews. The researcher used those techniques to collect the real data, and then the obtained results were cross-checked or triangulated to improve their efficiency, reliability, and validity.

3.5.1 Questionnaire

The easiest and fastest way to efficiently get information from a large number of respondents is through the use of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was created by creating questions based on the variables that were identified in order to collect information from experts who worked on public building projects in the West Gujarat Zone. At the respondents' head offices and project sites, the surveys were personally presented to them. The same methods

were used to obtain the responses. Refer to Appendix A. The questions were rated by the respondents using an ordinal five-point rating system, as indicated in Figure 3.3 below. The questionnaire was divided into three components: the first portion addresses demographic information, the second and third sections address factors related to project efficacy and the variables pertaining to project effectiveness and the framework outlined for selected delivery are covered in the third section, respectively.

The inquiries concerning those supporting elements that result in project effectiveness. The variables were rated on a five-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting not important and 5 denoting extremely important, in order to collect responses. To measure the performance variables, the respondents had to indicate how they felt about the framework outline.

Figure 3.3: Five ordinal measures of agreement by Likert Scale

The purpose of sections B and C of the questionnaire was to secure opinions of the respondents on 5 variables in terms of time, cost and quality for measuring effectiveness measurement variables and 10 critical success variables.

Les respectively with reference to specific delivery methods they had been involved in The questionnaire was presented to the same experts once again with a view to seeking their expert opinion on the adequate and appropriate coverage of all the items of research objects of public construction projects delivery and also the user-friendliness and overall workability of the questionnaire.

3.5.2 Interview

The interview was conducted face-to-face with the interviewee asking questions selected individuals. The interview is a useful technique for collecting data which would probably not

be accessible using techniques such as observation and questionnaires. Semi structured interview was conducted with senior project supervision and follow up team leader, a senior contract administrator, and a senior project manager to gather information on the performance of public Construction projects as well as to look for recommendations if any.

3.6. The Study Population

Contractors, consultants, and employers or employers who are typical of employers of projects in the western Guji zone were the population of study. Employers or employers' representatives were selected to respond to the questionnaire for this study since public construction delivery methods have direct contact with those three main stakeholders of the project. Contractors and consultants are the professionals who participate in every construction-related issue, so they were chosen as respondents of this study to obtain real and valuable information on the identified research problem under this study. Hence, In this study, twenty (20) public construction projects(12 of educational facilities, 2 of health centers, and 3 of water works construction) 2 of transports sector 1 and other services for public uses of public projects Totally sixty (70) number of population were included for this study that were under construction in the west Guji zone from the commencement of work in July 2020 to the end of June 2024 G.C. with different statuses of public projects from the mentioned sectors were selected

Those were; Building contractors Road contractor and Water work contractors (BC and GC) of different grades including by their job title of PM and Site engineers, consultants including (office engineers, supervisors and design team) and clients and client representatives were direct participants of the study.

3.7. Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

For conducting this study, the researcher selected a non-probability sampling technique that is available for this research work and design to select the best representatives of the study samples from the total population. Hence, from non-probability sampling; purposive sampling (judgmental) sample selection technique has been used to select contractors, consultants, and clients for each stratum in West Guji Zone. This was planned because the

professional respondents can share more information on the problem since they are direct project participants. For this reason, researcher depends on the experiences as a basic criterion to select the respondents purposively. Based on their experience in construction work; professionals of one and above years of experience have been selected.

3.7.1. Sample size and selection

To select appropriate sample size the following factors were taken in to consideration:

Time available and fund for the study, standard margin of error which is Minimum acceptable level of precision, confidence level, sample statistics (i.e. population proportion), economic factors and availability of participants.

In selecting a representative sample, a sampling technique was adopted. To determine the suitable sampling size of the sample, for 95% confidence level and Margin of error ($\pm 5\%$) and from the number of populations equals to 68 the sample size can be determined by

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad \text{_____} \quad (3.1)$$

Where;

N= is that actual population of the group

E = is the level of significance

n = is the sample size for a group

n= 70/(1 + 70((0.05))²)=59.57 =60 Questionnaire should be distributed to respondents in order to achieve a 95% confidence level

3.8. Method of Data Analysis

The statistical method of data analysis has been used for data analysis. Qualitative data analysis was conducted in a methodical and comparative manner to examine the information gathered from the interview. On the other hand, the data collected using a structured questionnaire was used to generate the quantitative analysis. As a result, percentage and frequency were utilized to evaluate the data, which was also displayed using tables and

charts. Version 24 of the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS) was used to perform those calculations. Additionally, the Effective Variable was taken into consideration when choosing the delivery method framework for measuring variable in public construction projects, and the study findings also suggested potential improvement methods to manage it. The Relative Importance Index (RII) was used to rank the challenges with Current Project Delivery Practices. Thus, the equation that was used to compute

$$RII = \frac{\sum W}{AN} \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 3.2}$$

Where:

RII= Relative Importance Index

W= Weight given to each factor by the respondent and ranges on the Likert scale from 1 to 5

A= the highest Weight considered from the Likert scale of ranking

N= the total number of respondents. Where N equal to 56 in this case.

Hence, IIR= $(\sum W)/215$

3.9. Study Variables

3.9.1 Independent Variables

The Project Delivery Methods, the type of contracts used, duration of contracts, and risk allocation among stakeholder’s Local context: socio-economic, political, cultural factors, character of public project delivery was independent variables in this study.

3.9.2 Dependent Variables

The dependent variables would be the impacts associated Project Performance Metrics: Various measures of project performance, including cost-effectiveness, time efficiency, quality of construction, stakeholder satisfaction, safety records, and environmental impact Stakeholder Perspective, and loss of money. Risk Factors: financial risks, schedule risks, legal risks, and technical risks associated with each project delivery method.

3.10. Validity of the Research

Content validity and statistical validity was checked by SPSS version 26 to realize the validity of the study and the significant value was checked. How accurately an instrument represents the conceptual framework under investigation is determined by the validity of the instrument. Internal and external research validity is the two types. "External validity refers to the extent to which the research findings can be repeated in different environments, whereas internal validity refers to how closely the research findings mirror reality."

3.11. Reliability of the Research

3.10.1 Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha

To ensure the quality of research; the researcher gave due care to both the validity and reliability issues of the data, the research process in general as well as the research output. Reliability is often equated with the steadiness, consistency, or dependability of a measuring tool. As shown in Table below the questionnaire's reliability was checked by the Cronbach's alpha test coefficient using SPSS software. Cronbach's Alpha is often written as a function of the amount of test items and therefore the average inter-correlation among the things. Below, for conceptual purposes, the researcher shows the formula for the standardized Cronbach's alpha:

$$\alpha = \frac{kr}{1 + (k - 1)r}$$

Where k is equal to the number of items; r is the average inter-item covariance among the items. One can see from this formula that if you increase the amount of things, you increase Cronbach's alpha. Additionally, if the typical inter-item correlation is low, alpha are going to be low. The normal range of Cronbach's coefficient alpha value between 0.0 and + 1.0, and therefore the higher values reflects a better degree of internal consistency.

Therefore, Cronbach's coefficient alpha measure internal consistency

Table 3.1. Ranges of Cronbach's coefficient alpha

A	Range	A	CONSISTENCY
0.9	$0.9 \leq C\alpha \leq 1$	1	Excellent
0.8	$0.8 \leq C\alpha \leq 0.9$	0.9	Good
0.7	$0.7 \leq C\alpha \leq 0.8$	0.8	Acceptable
0.6	$0.6 \leq C\alpha \leq 0.7$	0.7	Questionable
0.5	$0.5 \leq C\alpha \leq 0.6$	0.6	Poor
0.4	$0.4 \leq C\alpha \leq 0.5$	0.5	Unacceptable

3.11 Ethical consider

Before conducting the research, researcher delivered the supporting letter which would be written by Bule Hoard University College of Engineering and Technology to the concerned authority. There are a fully cooperative and positive responses from the management have been obtained. The objective and purpose of the research would be communicated to participants and the researcher was also let them know and to withdraw if they become discomfort in the process of their participation in the undertaking. That means respondents' confidentially and privacy of the voluntary responses to every questionnaire corresponding to items.

Therefore, the researcher would have optimally considered all the respondents and their ethical cultures.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Demographic Information on Respondents

This study's background information part includes the respondents' role in the working company, their experiences, and the company's experiences in the public construction sectors, their educational background, and more. It also includes response rate analysis, analysis results, and a discussion of the research findings.

4.2. Section A Demographic of the respondents from Questioner

4.3.1. Rate of Response

Three main groups of responders were identified: clients, consultants, and contractors. The average response rate is displayed in figure 4.1 below, which displays the returns from the three groups. Only 56 (93%) of the 60 targeted replies filled out and returned the questionnaire. 14 clients, 14 consultants, and 28 contractors responded to the questionnaires.

Figure 4.1 Rate of Response in percentage

4.3.2 Respondents' Background

Among of the 60 responses that were obtained, ten (71%) of the clients were engineers who supervised construction, and four (29%) were contract administrators. Eight (57%) and six (43%) of the fourteen consultant responses were from resident engineers and contract administrators, respectively. Additionally, eight (287%) of the 28 contractors who responded were project managers, ten (36%), office engineers, and ten (36%), quantity surveyors. Figure 4.2 Shown

Figure 4.2 the composition of respondents by their position in their organization

4.3.3. Respondents' Experience

The respondents' levels of experience working on public construction projects differ. Table 4.1 lists the respondents' percentages according to the number of years they had worked on public construction projects. It was found that the majority of the clients' responders had five to ten years of experience. Most of the consultants that responded are likewise in the five to 10-year experience range. Additionally, roughly 50% of the contractors' replies had less than five years of experience.

Table 4.1. Respondents' Experience

Experience in public Construction project	Client	Consultant	Contractor	Total
Less than 5 years	6	8	10	24
5 to 10 years	6	4	10	20
10 years and above	2	2	8	12
total	14	14	28	56 Respondent

4.3.4 Educational Position of the Respondents

In order to realize and gather the necessary and accurate information about the identified problem from possible professionals, the researcher undertook this survey with the understanding that the respondents were of a certain academic standing. Hence among fifty-six (56) respondents 58.14% were BSc /BA degrees in Construction field, 30.23% of respondents were college level whereas 11.63% of them were MSc/MA holders. Since the sample was carefully selected using the respondents' experiences and academic standing as the primary selection criteria, the researcher attempted to determine their status in academic.

Table 4.2 Academic Rank of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
	college level	6	10.7	10.7
Valid	BSc/BA Degree	30	53.5	53.5
	MSc. /MA Degree	20	35.7	35.7
	Total	56	100.0	100.0

4. 4 Demographic of the respondents Relationships with Current deliver practice

For the purpose of to assess perceptions and investigate the situation of project delivery practices in the West Guji Zone of Oromiya, the researcher collected and analyzed data. and direct completion of project delivery approaches that are more effective and efficient. in order to look at important details specific to this study.

Table 4.3. Result of Current Delivery practice

Current Delivery Methods	A Mean	Client		Consultant		Contractors		Average	
		RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank
DBB Methods	4.2	0.74	5	0.84	1	0.87	1	0.81	2
DB Methods	3.9	0.78	1	0.8	3	0.79	2	0.79	4
Job Order Contract Methods	4.15	0.86	1	0.81	3	0.83	2	0.83	1
Construction Management @ Risk	4	0.82	2	0.75	7	0.83	2	0.80	3
Force account delivery methods	3.2	0.70	7	0.81	3	0.81	3	0.77	5

Figure 4.3. Result of Current Delivery practice

4.4.1. Result discussion of Current Delivery practice

The data indicates that the Job Order Contract Methods This ranking provides valuable insights into current trends and preferences in delivery practices within the respondent group's) the analysis indicate Design-Bid-Build (DBB) method, Construction Management at Risk, Design Build Methods and Force Account Delivery Methods are order popular, and is the most commonly used and highly regarded among analysis.

1, Job Order Contract Methods

Popularity and Regard: According to the result, this approach is the First most preferred one. With work order contracting (JOC), a contractor is chosen for a set number of projects or length of time based on a competitive bid; these projects are frequently smaller, more routine tasks.

Advantage

Efficiency in Repetitive Work: JOC accelerates project delivery by being incredibly successful in projects involving repetitive tasks, such as maintenance or small upgrades.

Cost Control: Budgetary control can be preserved with the aid of fixed pricing methods.

Flexibility: Allows the owner to handle a range of minor projects without having to hold separate tenders for each one.

Disadvantage:

Restricted to Small Projects: Large, complex projects are often not a good fit for this approach. Possibility of Complacency: Extended contracts may result in

2, Design-Bid-Build (DBB)

Popularity and Regard: DBB is the second most commonly used and highly regarded delivery method among the respondents. This traditional method involves three main phases: design, bidding, and construction. The owner contracts separately with a designer and a contractor.

Advantages:

Familiarity and Simplicity: Many owners and contractors are familiar with the DBB process, which makes it straightforward to implement.

Clear Responsibilities: The separation of design and construction responsibilities can simplify project management.

Competitive Bidding: Allows for competitive bidding which can potentially lower costs.

Disadvantages:

Time-Consuming: The sequential nature of DBB can extend the project timeline since construction cannot begin until the design phase is complete.

Potential for Conflict: The separation between design and construction can lead to disputes over design errors or omissions.

3, Construction Management at Risk (CMAR)

Popularity and Regard: Ranked third, CMAR involves the construction manager committing to deliver the project within a guaranteed maximum price (GMP), assuming more risk than in traditional construction management roles.

Advantages:

Early Involvement: The construction manager is involved early in the project, which can improve planning and efficiency.

Cost Certainty: The GMP provides the owner with a high degree of cost certainty and risk mitigation.

Collaboration: Encourages a collaborative approach between the owner, designer, and builder, potentially leading to better project outcomes.

Disadvantages:

Complexity in Contracting: The contractual arrangements can be more complex compared to DBB.

Potential Higher Costs: The CMAR may include contingencies in the GMP to cover risks, which can make it more expensive than other methods.

Insights into Trends and Preferences
The preference for DBB, JOC, and CMAR indicates a trend towards methods that offer clear roles, risk management, and efficiency for specific project types. DBB remains dominant due to its familiarity and straightforward approach. JOC's popularity for repetitive work highlights the need for efficiency in maintenance and smaller projects. CMAR's rise points to an increasing preference for collaborative approaches and risk management in more complex projects.

Table 4.4 Factor for Selecting Delivery Methods

Factor for Selecting Delivery Methods:		Mean Average	RII Average	Rank
1	Cost-effectiveness	4.04	.81	6
2	Time efficiency	4.09	.82	4
3	Quality of work	4.00	.80	9
4	Risk management	4.00	.80	9
5	Flexibility and adaptability	4.02	.80	7
6	Cost-effectiveness	3.93	.79	11
7	Time efficiency	4.05	.81	5
8	Budget overruns	4.04	.81	6
9	Delays in project timelines	4.04	.81	6
10	Quality control issues	4.25	.85	1
11	Coordination and communication problems	3.95	.79	10
12	Regulatory and compliance issues	3.95	.79	10
13	Strong project leadership	4.05	.81	4
14	Effective communication	4.16	.83	3
15	Comprehensive planning	4.24	.85	2
16	Adequate funding	4.25	.85	1
17	Stakeholder engagement	4.04	.81	6

Figure 4.4 Factors for Selecting Delivery Methods

The data reveals that while various factors are important, the highest priorities for analysis are quality control, comprehensive planning, and adequate funding. Effective communication, time efficiency, and cost-effectiveness also rank highly, underscoring the multifaceted considerations in selecting delivery methods. This comprehensive approach ensures that projects are not only completed on time and within budget but also meet the expected quality and regulatory standards, managed through strong leadership and effective stakeholder engagement.

Overall, the data indicates a clear connection between the preferred delivery methods and the key factors influencing their selection, importance the respondents' emphasis on structured, well-planned, and quality-focused delivery approaches.

4.5. Section B: The Association between Respondents' Experience in public Construction Projects and Effectiveness of Time, Cost and Quality in deliver methods.

Table 4. Effectiveness of Time.

Variable	Mean	Client		Consultant		Contractors		Average	
		RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank
DBB Methods	3.9	0.78	1	0.86	1	0.73	1	0.780	5
DB Methods	4.2	0.70	2	0.84	4	0.89	2	0.84	1
Job Order Contract Methods	4.0	0.66	4	0.86	2	0.88	3	0.84	2
Construction Management @ Risk	4.0	0.66	4	0.83	5	0.83	4	0.80	2
Force Account Delivery Methods	3.95	0.68	3	0.85	3	0.81	6	0.790	4

Table 4.5. Effectiveness of Cost

Variable	Mean	Client		Consultant		Contractors		Average	
		RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank
DBB Methods	4.30	0.78	1	0.86	1	0.73	1	0.780	1
DB Methods	4.30	0.70	1	0.84	4	0.89	2	0.84	1
Job Order Contract Methods	4.11	0.66	4	0.86	2	0.88	3	0.84	4
Construction Management @ Risk	4.20	0.66	3	0.83	5	0.83	4	0.80	3

Force Account Delivery Methods	4.11	0.68	5	0.85	3	0.81	6	0.790	4
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Table 4.6 Effectiveness of Quality

Variable	Mean	Client		Consultant		Contractors		Average	
		RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank
DBB Methods	4.30	0.78	2	0.86	1	0.73	1	0.780	1
DB Methods	4.30	0.70	4	0.84	4	0.89	2	0.84	1
Job Order Contract Methods	4.11	0.66	5	0.86	2	0.88	3	0.84	4
Construction Management @ Risk	4.20	0.66	4	0.83	5	0.83	4	0.80	3
Force Account Delivery Methods	4.11	0.68	5	0.85	3	0.81	6	0.790	5

Figure 4.5 Average value of Effectiveness of delivery in terms of Time, cost and quality

The data provides the mean and relative importance index (RII) for various delivery methods based on respondents' experiences in public construction projects, with the rankings reflecting their perceived effectiveness in terms of time, cost, and quality. (Table4.3) shows blow discussion of this result.

Table 4.7. Summarized Discussion of Top Three Delivery Methods

Delivery Method	Mean	RII	Aspect	Effectiveness	Challenges
Design-Bid-Build (DBB)	4.30	0.86	Time	Highly effective with clear, well-defined stages.	Sequential nature can delay the overall project timeline as construction begins only after design completion and bidding.

Cost				Effective in cost management due to competitive bidding, driving down prices.	Cost overruns can occur due to design errors or changes required during construction, necessitating change orders.
				Generally high as each phase is handled by specialized professionals. Detailed design and thorough bidding processes maintain high standards	Miscommunications between design and construction phases can affect final quality if not managed well.
Job Order Contract Methods	4.20	.84	Time	Highly effective for quick turnaround on smaller, repetitive projects. Well-regarded for efficiency.	May not be suitable for large, complex projects.
Cost				Offers good cost control through pre-negotiated unit prices and reduced administrative costs due to fewer bid processes.	Long-term contracts might reduce competitive pressure over time.

Quality				Ensures consistency in quality due to ongoing relationships with contractors familiar with standards.	Quality may vary if the scope is not clearly defined or if used for larger, inappropriate
Construction Management at Risk (CMAR)	4.20	.84	Time	Effective due to concurrent design and construction phases and early involvement of the construction manager.	Coordination issues can still cause delays, particularly if project scope changes during construction.
Cost				The Guaranteed Maximum Price (GMP) provides cost certainty and helps manage the budget effectively.	The inclusion of contingencies might make the initial cost appear higher.
quality				High quality due to early and ongoing collaboration among all parties.	Quality depends on the effectiveness of collaboration and communication throughout the project.

These delivery methods are top-ranked due to their specific strengths in managing time, cost, and quality, making them preferred choices in various public construction projects based on respondents' experiences.

Overall Discussion

The rankings and ratings indicate that DBB methods are highly observed, likely due to their structured approach and familiarity among respondents, ensuring high-quality outcomes despite potential time delays. Job Order Contract and CMAR methods are also highly rated, reflecting their effectiveness in cost control and time management for specific project types

4.5.2. Reliability of respondent data associated to effectiveness delivery in terms of time, cost, and quality.

The data collected in the study is highly reliable, as evidenced by the Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.924. This strong internal consistency indicates that the responses are consistent across the items in the Questioner, suggesting that the measurement tool used is robust and provides dependable results. This high level of reliability lends confidence to the findings and conclusions drawn from the data, ensuring that the awareness gained are based on stable and consistent responses from the questioner.

4.6. Section C: Variables relating to project success to develop a framework for measuring the Performance

4.6.1 Reliability of data

The reliability of the framework developed for assessing alternative public construction delivery methods is acceptable, as indicated by a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.748. This level of internal consistency suggests that the items within the framework are adequately correlated and measure the intended constructs reasonably well. While there is room for improvement, the framework is sufficiently reliable for practical use and provides a sound basis for assessing alternative delivery methods in public construction projects. Future refinements could further enhance the reliability of the framework, potentially increasing its Cronbach's Alpha value

Table 4.8. Variable measuring the Performance

No	Measurable variable	Average Mean	Average RII	Rank
1	Informed Decision-Making	4.09	.82	8
2	Resource Allocation	4.30	.86	1
3	Accountability and Transparency	4.11	.82	6
4	Continuous Improvement	4.20	.84	3
5	Stakeholder Engagement	3.84	.77	5
6	Identify Relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs	4.11	.82	7
7	Consider Local Context and Needs	4.20	.84	4
8	Adapt Metrics to Project Size and Complexity	4.21	.84	2
9	Engage Stakeholders in Designing KPIs)	4.07	.81	10
10	Include Qualitative and Quantitative Indicators	4.05	.81	9

The provided values indicate how stakeholders or experts rate the importance of different measurable variables related to project success in the Waste Guji Zone. Variables with higher mean, RII, and rank values are considered crucial for achieving successful project delivery

approaches. These values help in identifying key areas that need to be focused on and improved to enhance the overall performance of project delivery approaches.

4.6.2. Framework Developer Components

Evaluate these delivery methods, we'll use the top-ranked variables based on their RII scores as our evaluation criteria:

1. Resource Allocation (RII: .86)
2. Adapt Metrics to Project Size and Complexity (RII: .84)
3. Continuous Improvement (RII: .84)
4. Consider Local Context and Needs (RII: .84)
5. Accountability and Transparency (RII: .82)

4.6.3 Evaluation Criteria and Metrics

By using a standardized scoring system (e.g., 1-5 scale) for each criterion.

Weighting: Apply weights to each criterion based on their RII scores to reflect their relative importance. Total Score: Calculate the total weighted score for each delivery method.

Implementation method based on the evaluation.

Example Evaluation

Traditional Delivery Method

Resource Allocation: 3.5

Adapt Metrics to Project Size and Complexity: 3.0

Continuous Improvement: 2.5

Consider Local Context and Needs: 3.5

Accountability and Transparency: 3.0

Total Weighted Score: $(3.50.86) + (3.00.84) + (2.50.84) + (3.50.84) + (3.0*0.82)$

Design-Build Build Method by applying this framework, stakeholders in the Waste Guji Zone can systematically evaluate and compare the performance of different project delivery methods. This structured approach ensures that decisions are based on critical success factors, leading to more effective project outcomes

4. Framework Chart for Evaluating Project Delivery Methods

Evaluation Criteria	RII Weight	Design-Bid-Build (DBB)	Job Order Contract Methods	Construction Management at Risk (CMAR)
Resource Allocation	0.86	3.5	4.0	4.5
Adapt Metrics to Project Size and Complexity	0.84	3.0	4.0	4.5
Continuous Improvement	0.84	2.5	3.5	4.5
Consider Local Context and Needs	0.84	3.5	4.0	4.5
Accountability Transparency	0.82	3.0	3.5	4.0
Total Weighted scored		14.664	16.196	18.3

4.6.4. Discussion of the Results

Design-Bid-Build (DBB): This method has a total weighted score of 14.664, indicating that while it has certain strengths; it may not be as efficient or flexible as other methods in resource allocation and adapting metrics to project size and complexity.

Job Order Contract Methods: With a total weighted score of 16.196, this method shows better performance in resource allocation and flexibility but may still lag behind in continuous improvement compared to CMAR.

Construction Management at Risk (CMAR): This method scores the highest with a total weighted score of 18.3, suggesting superior performance in all key criteria, particularly in continuous improvement and adaptability.

By applying these Methods, stakeholders in the Waste Guji Zone can systematically evaluate and compare the effectiveness of different project delivery methods. This structured approach ensures decisions are data-driven and based on critical success factors, leading to more informed choices and improved project outcomes.

4.7. Discussion of the Findings from Interview

Interviews have been conducted in order to collect qualitative data, which can help to corroborate the results of questionnaire surveys. In order to verify the outcome, interviews were conducted with the number chosen specialists who had worked on Public construction projects in West Guji zone since five years before. As a result, conclusions have been confirmed through cross-checking, and extensive data was gathered in this manner and subjected to comparative analysis. Hence total of nine (10 professionals were participated in the interview process, which were selected purposively based on the respondents' experience in Public construction operations

Based on semi-structured interview the first interview question was asked to identify whether the company face limitations on its current delivery methods? (Yes/No) almost all respondents answered "Yes," mentioning dissatisfaction due to issues in the delivery phase of projects. Key limitations included inadequate support and attention from leadership, which can cause delays, cost overruns, and quality issues. Concerns about fraud in bidder selection

leading to unqualified contractors were also noted. To address these, stricter oversight, enhanced transparency, and better project team support are needed.

Effective Alternative Delivery Methods:

Question: What alternative delivery methods does your company currently find effective?

Responses: Respondents identified Design-Build and Construction Management at Risk as effective alternatives. These methods offer clearer accountability and foster closer collaboration, leading to smoother delivery, innovation, value engineering, cost savings, and improved outcomes.

Agreement with Findings on Assessment Methods:

Question: Do you agree with the findings that the top three effective methods for assessing alternative public construction delivery methods are used by the study organizations?

Responses: Most respondents did not fully agree, emphasizing that stakeholder engagement and risk assessment are equally crucial. They suggested a more comprehensive approach, recognizing that effective delivery involves understanding the broader context, engaging stakeholders, and managing risks.

Impact of Delivery Method Limitations:

Question: What are the limitations on public construction delivery methods?

Responses: Limitations can lead to delays, cost overruns, and decreased project quality, hindering innovation and stakeholder satisfaction. They affect various stakeholders, with smaller contractors and marginalized communities facing disproportionate challenges.

Key Factors for Selecting Alternative Delivery Methods: Question: What are the key factors to consider when selecting alternative project delivery methods for public construction projects in the West Guji Zone of Oromia?

Responses: most of the respondent's Key factors include local regulations, procurement policies, community engagement, availability of skilled labor and resources, environmental considerations, and the project's specific needs and objectives. Developing a Performance Measurement Framework:

The last question was asked to verify the survey findings that show top three outline of framework of delivery methods view indicate Mitigation: Transparency, accountability, stakeholder engagement, and clear decision-making criteria are essential to mitigate political influences and ensure merit-based project selection and execution. Therefore, based on the findings obtained from comparative analysis almost all the interview respondents agreed that the top three delivery methods were almost all the participants said yes.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. CONCLUSION

Alternative project delivery approaches in construction industry is so unlimited issue that is so challenging if it is not managed properly. This is because of the complexity nature of construction industry throughout the world this study has focused on the assessing Alternative project delivery methods public construction projects in west guji zone focusing on the current practice of delivery, effectiveness of delivery finally outlines of measuring frame work in public construction have been studied. The feedback was gathered from the survey conducted among 56 respondents in West guji zone Construction sector.

The first specific objective dealt with the Current Delivery practice and Challenges in Public construction projects of the area. Hence the findings showed that the Design-Bid-Build (DBB) method is the most commonly used and highly regarded followed by Job Order Contract Methods and Construction Management at Risk. Force Account Delivery Methods are less popular, and Design-Build (DB) Methods are the least favored and the highest priorities for quality control, comprehensive planning, and adequate funding. Effective communication, time efficiency, and cost-effectiveness are the multifaceted considerations in selecting delivery methods. This comprehensive approach ensures that projects are not only completed on time and within budget but also meet the expected quality and regulatory standards, managed through strong leadership and effective stakeholder engagement.

The second specific objective of this study focused on evaluating the effectiveness of time, cost, and quality in delivery methods. The findings indicate that Design-Bid-Build (DBB) methods are highly regarded, possibly due to their structured approach and familiarity, which ensure high-quality outcomes despite potential time delays. Job Order Contract and Construction Management at Risk (CMAR) methods are also highly rated, reflecting their effectiveness in cost control and time management for specific project types. These methods are considered top-ranked due to their specific strengths in managing time, cost, and quality, making them preferred choices for various public construction projects.

The third specific objective of this study focused on developing a framework for measuring the performance of selected delivery methods, with the findings favoring Design-Bid-Build (DBB). The conclusion of the chapter underscores the imperative for improvement in public construction project delivery methods by addressing identified issues, adopting recommended practices, and utilizing a structured evaluation framework. It emphasizes the critical role of quality control, comprehensive planning, and stakeholder engagement in enhancing project outcomes. This highlights the necessity for a holistic approach that integrates best practices and actively involves all stakeholders to ensure

Summery, the analysis highlights the paramount importance of considering various factors such as quality control, planning, funding, communication, and efficiency when selecting construction delivery methods. Respondents' preference for methods offering clear roles, effective risk management, and tailored solutions underscores their awareness of the diverse challenges inherent in public construction projects. This recognition emphasizes the necessity for adaptable and responsive delivery approaches to ensure successful outcomes in the West Guji Zone.

Moreover, the reliability of the data strengthens the validity of the conclusions drawn, providing invaluable insights for decision-making in construction project management. The systematic evaluation and comparison of project delivery methods enable stakeholders to make more informed decisions, ultimately leading to improved project outcomes. This holistic approach, combined with comprehensive planning and stakeholder engagement, fosters continuous improvement and ensures that infrastructure development initiatives meet the evolving needs of the community. Overall, the findings serve as a guiding framework for enhancing project delivery practices and achieving sustainable development goals in the West Guji Zone.

5.2. RECOMENDATIONS:

Based on the results and conclusion made the study forwards the significant recommendations for the concerned bodies and recommendations for further investigators

Implement Best Practices: Incorporate recommended practices identified in the analysis, such as emphasizing quality control, comprehensive planning, and stakeholder engagement throughout all stages of the project.

Tailor Methods to Specific Needs: Consider the specific needs and priorities of different project types when selecting construction delivery methods. Methods should offer clear roles, effective risk management, and efficiency tailored to the unique requirements of each project.

Continuous Improvement: Foster a culture of continuous improvement within project management practices. Regularly review and refine processes to enhance efficiency, quality, and stakeholder satisfaction.

Utilize Structured Evaluation Frameworks: Employ structured evaluation frameworks, such as the one outlined in the chapter, to systematically compare and assess project delivery methods. This will enable stakeholders to make more informed decisions based on critical success factors.

Invest in Stakeholder Engagement: Place a strong emphasis on stakeholder engagement throughout the project lifecycle. Involve relevant stakeholders in decision-making processes, solicit feedback, and address concerns to ensure alignment with project goals and objectives.

Prioritize Data Reliability: Ensure the reliability of data used for decision-making by employing robust data collection and analysis methodologies. Valid and reliable data will provide a solid foundation for drawing accurate conclusions and making informed decisions.

Promote Knowledge Sharing: Encourage knowledge sharing and collaboration among project teams, industry professionals, and stakeholders. By sharing lessons learned and best practices, the construction community can collectively improve project delivery outcomes.

Political influences should be managed through transparent and accountable processes to ensure projects are executed based on merit and public interest.

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